

A Review: Polymer and Their Need

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ABSTRACT: The electric transport in polymeric materials has developed into an increasingly significant topic of research due to the strong potential for solid state devices that polymeric materials have and because this field of study serves as a stepping stone towards the general theory of polymer physics. This page will provide comprehensive knowledge about polymers, which can inspire fresh investigation. This article discusses how polymers are made, their classifications, Development of New Drug Dosage Forms using Natural Polymers, Why Natural Polymers are Safe to Use, different sources of natural polymer, method of extraction of natural polymer, how important they are to paper and textile industry, pharmaceutical industry, in daily life, and in cosmetics. It also discusses some cutting-edge polymer-related procedures that have recently been created. This article's accord a compilation of all available information about polymers, including their natural sources, uses, and applications. The scientific community will be persuaded by this article to continue their research in the subject of polymers by retaining their interest in it. This is because more natural polymers are required in pharmaceuticals because they have less side effects and are more stable.

Key Words: Polymer, Natural polymer, Source of Natural Polymer

INTRODUCTION:

The polymer is derived from the Greek word 'poly' (meaning “many”) and ‘Mero’(meaning“parts”). So, we can say that meaning of polymer is “ many parts.” Polymers are bulky molecules that contain molar mass polymers is ranging from thousand to millions. Almost 75 - 80 % of the organic chemical industry is dedicated to the production of polymers such as synthetic polymers e.g., plastic, textile fibres and synthetic rubbers also (Sen, 2019). Polymers are materials which contain many small molecules called monomers which can be linked together and forms a long chain which is known as macromolecules.

Monomers are obtained from low molecular weight, simple compounds and these are repeating units. In polymerisation the monomers are converted into polymer. Monomer should possess at least -

- Reactive functional groups

OR

- two bonding sites (multiple bonds)

Understand by an example- Take ethylene (as monomer) and form a polymer i.e., polyethylene. Their reaction given below

Fig:1 Example of Monomer (Sreedhar, 2005)

Almost all the cosmetic formulations which contain polymer are used as an essential class of raw materials, being important in the preparation of high-performance products. Their structures change and which promotes different functions such as rheology modifiers, their thickness, foam stabilizers and destabilizers, emulsifier, film former, fixative conditioning (Dias-Ferreira, et al., 2020) (Gawade, Chinke, & Alegaonkar, 2020) (Severino, et al., 2016).

Polymers are also pursued to be a good host material. When we study their physical properties such as optical absorption spectrum (one of the most essential tools for knowing electronic properties and band structures of pure and slew polymer). This spectra are reported earlier but it was only last decade that paid attention for evaluate the optical constant (such as refractive indices, absorption coefficient, etc) for pure and slew polymer (Alan G. MacDiarmid, 2001) (Jyoti Rozra, 2012) (Suman Mahendia, 2013) (Fernandes G. M., 2013).

Development of New Drug Dosage Forms using Natural Polymers:

Natural polymers play a pivotal role in advancing drug dosage forms, particularly in the creation of encapsulation systems for controlled release. For instance, chitosan, derived from shellfish, serves as an effective encapsulation material, allowing precise modulation of drug release rates. This strategy enhances therapeutic efficacy by ensuring a sustained and targeted

delivery, reducing side effects, and improving patient compliance. Biodegradable implants, utilizing polymers like polylactic acid (PLA), represent another frontier. These implants gradually release drugs, addressing the need for sustained treatment while minimizing the risk of long-term exposure and associated adverse effects. In oral drug delivery, cellulose derivatives are employed to enhance stability, control release kinetics, and facilitate convenient administration through tablets or capsules (Radha Rani Earle, 2016).

Why Natural Polymers are Safe to Use?

The safety of natural polymers stems from their inherent biocompatibility, originating from biological sources, and their low immunogenicity, minimizing the likelihood of adverse immune reactions. Biodegradability is a key safety feature, ensuring that these polymers break down into harmless byproducts, reducing the risk of accumulation and potential toxicity over time. Further, their historical use, as seen with gelatine in pharmaceuticals, establishes a track record of safety. Embracing natural polymers aligns with sustainability objectives, as they are often derived from renewable sources, making them not only safe for medical applications but also environmentally friendly. The combination of these attributes positions natural polymers as integral components in the development of safe and effective drug delivery systems (Radha Rani Earle, 2016).

Synthesis of Polymer-The process of combining many small molecules like as monomer through covalent bonded chain or network known as polymerization . During polymerization some of the chemical groups may be lost from monomer and it is happening in the polymerization of PET polyester. The monomers such as terephthalic acid (HOOC-C₆H₄-COOH) and ethylene glycol (HO-CH₂-CH₂-OH) but the repeating unit is -OC-C₆H₄-COO-CH₂-CH₂-O- , that two monomers are combined together with the loss of water molecules and that monomer known as repeat unit or monomer residue.

The synthetic methods of Polymers are generally divided into two categories

1. Chain polymerization
2. Step growth polymerization

The chain polymerization has monomers of different types are added into one chain at a time only like as polystyrene. But in step growth polymerization have chains of monomers that combine with one another directly such as polyester (L.H, 2006). It can be divided into poly

condensation in this process we get low molar as product and it is happening every reaction step and polyaddition.

Fig:3 Example of chain polymerization

Fig:4 Polymer extraction from bamboo

Classification of polymer-

Polymers are classified based on some given aspects -

1. By structure
2. By origin
3. By thermal response
4. By monomer
5. By mode of formation
6. By application and physical property
7. By Tacticity

1) **Classification based on structure**– In which classified on the base of their structure as one line or branching.

- **Linear polymer**-These types of polymers have straight and long chains it does not contains any branches. Some of their examples are high density

polythene, Polyvinyl chloride, and polyester (Zhao Z. R., 2019) (Meister, 2014) (Disha Experts Team, 2019).

- **Branched Chain polymer-** Polymers have monomer, and in branched chain polymer the monomers are units and forms a combine formed it is not only combine for producing the linear chain but also forms branches of different length with main chain: e.g. low density polythene are amylopectin and glycogen (Zhao Z. R., 2019) (Elnashar, 2011) (Aguilar, 2019).

Fig:4 Branched – Chain Polymer (Saeed, Smart Pharmaceutical Polymers Classification and Applications: A Review, 2021)

- **Cross linked polymers or network polymer:** -These types of polymers have a long straight chain but are attached by strong covalent bonds by their chains. In which the linear polymers originally formed and are attached together for create a network structure of three-dimensional form. e.g., Bakelite, Melamine and Chrome (Abd El Aty A. F., 2017) (Mahajan, 2011).

Fig:5 Network Polymer (Saeed, Smart Pharmaceutical Polymers Classification and Applications: A Review, 2021)

- 2) **Classification based upon their origin** -Polymers can be classified in many ways. The most simply classification is the basis of their origin, it is classified in given parts are- (Isha Saini, 2013)

- **Natural polymers-** Some Polymer such as sugars,nucleotides,proteins,lipids which are obtain by animals and plants.

Fig:6Sources of Natural Polymer(Gerardo Leyva Gomez, 2018)

- **Semi synthetic polymers-** These types of polymers such as cellulose and vulcanized rubber are major and obtained by chemically modified natural.
- **Synthetic polymers-** It includes fibres and plastic rubber and are commonly used in daily life. These types of polymers are made by human(Ash, 2004)(Sekhri, 2016).

3) Classification on basis thermal response -

- **Thermoplastic polymer:**These types of polymers are hard on coding and exist soft in hot condition. It includes either linear or branched chain type polymer. We give them a desired shape with heating and subsequent cool at room temperature.e.g.,PE,PVC,PP, PS etc.
- **Thermosetting polymer:** These are hard on heating under pressure and are not remould and infusible on further heating. Theseare existed in cross linked polymers and they are not reused. e.g. Bakelite(Gupta, 2016).

Fig:7Thermosetting polymer(Saeed, Smart Pharmaceutical Polymers Classification and Applications: A Review, 2021)

4) Classification based on monomer —

- **Homo polymer-** These types of polymer consist an identical monomer and are formed summation of same types of monomers e.g. polyethylene,PVC, poly propene, polyisoprene (Zhao Z. R., 2019)(McCrum, 1997)(Meister, 2014)(Rezwan, 2006)(Gupta, 2016).

Fig:8 Four strategies of polymers(Saeed, Smart Pharmaceutical Polymers Classification and Applications: A Review, 2021)

- **Copolymers-** These types of polymers contain a monomer of different chemical structure and formed by summation of various monomers e.g., Buna-S, Buna-N,polyester, alkyd resins (Ash, 2004)(Sekhri, 2016)(Disha Experts Team, 2019)(Hassan, 2019)(Gupta, 2016).

Fig:9 The copolymer of methyl methacrylate and methacrylic acid(Saeed, Smart Pharmaceutical Polymers Classification and Applications: A Review, 2021)

5) Classification based upon the mode of formation —

- **Addition polymer-** It is understood through their name and these types of polymers are formed through repeating monomer and combine which are classifies into two parts i.e.
 1. Homopolymer
 2. Copolymer

(These are discussed above in classification based upon monomer.)

- **Condensation polymer-** In which involves two or more different monomeric molecules and condense together and eliminate some cases water etc, bi-functional or tri-functional.e.g., nylon, terylene, Bakeliteetc(Thakur, 2016)(Awad, 2017)(Abd El Aty A. F., 2017).

6) Classification their application and physical property –

- **Elastomer-** These are solid in nature and contains rubber like elasticity. Rubber is most abundant and important in all elastomers. They contain isoprene as monomer. Most of rubber is used in the United States today as synthetic are called styrene butadiene rubber (SBR). It is stretched due to weak intermolecular forces and it is amorphous in nature alsoe.g., natural rubber, BUNA-S, BUNA-N.
- **Plastic-** From recent studies approximately 60 billion pounds of plastics are consumed in America. In which shape of polymer is hard and tough utility articles through application of heat and pressure. These have partially crystalline structure.They are divided into two parts first is thermoplastic and thermosetting (these are discussed above). The thermoplastic is used in commercial; it includes the low-densitypolyethylene (LDPE) that have soft property and apply on formation of plastic bags,containers, textiles and electrical insulation, coating for product packaging the second form of polyethylene is high density polyethylene (HDPE) is greater rigid than LDPE and it is applied where the rigidity is important for formulation their major uses in plastic tubing,bottles, and bottle caps. e.g. polystyrene,PVC,PMMA.
- **Fibre-** Naturalfibres like as cotton, wool and silk which is used through human from centuries. Man made fibres include nylon,polyester,rayon, and acrylic, it also includes that type of polymer which are contain long filament like material and their length is at least 100 times it is diameter and are converted into fibre, due to high intermolecular attraction forces like hydrogen bonding it is higher tensile strength. Nylon has specific properties it contains elasticity and electric resistance on large scale and has commercial application is used in clothing and carpeting.e.g.,nylon,terylene.

7) **Classification based on toxicity** - The term tacticity is understood as deposition of side groups in space. These are classified as following –

- **Isotactic polymer** - In which configuration of functional groups are deposited on the same side of the chain from head to tail.
- **Syndiotactic polymer**- If the functional groups are deposited on side groups is in alternating pattern.
- **Atactic polymer** -If the deposition of side groups is existed in random pattern around the main(Gupta, 2016)(Burke J., 1978)(Bhumika Mishra, 2015).

Fig:10 (a) Isotactic polymer, (b) Syndiotactic polymer, (c) Atactic polymer(Bhumika Mishra, 2015)

Extraction of polymer-

- **From Bamboo**-After being sliced into a thin bar (300mm x 30mm x 5mm³), bamboo had its fibre removed using three different techniques: steam, alkali, and chemical. First, 5 kg of bamboo strips were placed into an autoclave and heated to 175 °C at 0.8 MPa for 55 minutes while being depressurized nine times to remove ashes. After this, the bamboo strips were repeatedly washed in water and dried in an oven. Second, 5 kg of strips were put in a 1.5 N NaOH container. then heat at 70 °C for 5 hours. Thirdly, degumming was utilised in the chemical process, and this cure also utilised a high proportion of NaOH in comparison to the alkali solution. In comparison to untreated

as well as alkali process, chemical and steam explosion extraction reduced the tensile strength and modulus of fibre epoxy composites. Along with chemical extraction changing the chemical structure of fibres using chemicals, steam explosion damages fibres with high temperatures. Comparing an alkali process to a steam explosion and chemical extraction, the alkali process has little impact on the characteristics of fibres. In contrast to chemical and steam explosion extraction, alkali extraction had a high contact angle. Additionally, the greatest values in the alkali extraction of fibres are embedded length (L) and droplet height (h)(S.B. Fiber, 2020).

Types of Extraction	Parameter of Treatment	Megapascal(Mpa)	Modulus of Elasticity(Gpa)	Elongation at Break(Eb)(%)	Ref.
Mechanical method of manual splitting /hammering	Bamboo splitters into strips 2x2x30mm	830(0.57)	14.48(490)	5.85(0.15)	(Trujilo, 2014)
	Bamboo splitters into strips 30x15x1500 mm	252.93	32.1		(Shinde, 2018)
	Bamboo splitters into strips 1x0.14x200mm	179.4	8.7	2.02	(C. Ramprasad, 2018)
	First roller crusher, the Pin-roller, last boil 90°C for 10h	420±170	38.2±16.0	9.8±2.5	(Science, 2019)
	Novel purely mechanical , set length 5-40, thickness 5mm	750	38		(B. Lipp-symonowicz and S. Sztajnowski, 2011)
	Bamboo strips 2x2x20mm	1320(320)	30.9(0.22)	1.84(0.22)	(P. Rawatan and S. F.S Buluh, 2018)
	Softed in hot water,extracted mechanically using fine	1320(230)	42.0(0.32)	1.96(0.30)	(P. Rawatan and S. F.S Buluh, 2018)

	tweezers				
	Softed in hot water ,extracted mechanically using fine tweezers	1780(150)	26.8(0.06)	2.89(0.16)	(P. Rawatan and S. F.S Buluh, 2018)
	Softed in hot water ,extracted mechanically using fine tweezers	1520(300)	18.3(0.18)	2.80(0.31)	(P. Rawatan and S. F.S Buluh, 2018)
	Novel purely mechanized , Gage length(mm)5-40	775-860	42-46	1.7-1.9	(Sztajnowski , 2011)
Steam Explosion	Heated at 175°C,0.8MPa,1h for 9 times	383	28	2.82	(D.Chakraborty, 2006)
	180°C ,0.8MPa for 90 min, 9 times	615-862	35.45	4.11	(Dupeyre, 1997)
	170°C ,0.8MPa for 100 min, 8 times	441	35.9	1.3	(D.Chakraborty, 2006)
Chemical Extraction	Can 15g/L Na ₂ CO ₃	20.07			(D.Chakraborty, 2006)
	17.5% NaOH and 17.5% KOH at RT for 1h	11.87			(F. Tianshun, 2017)
	0.1 N NaOH at 35°C for 75h	12.6			(F. Tianshun, 2017)
	0.7% NaClO ₂ at 90°C for 1h treat with 2% NaHSO ₃ at RT for 15min	13.5			(F. Tianshun, 2017)
	20g/L NaOH ,5g/L Na ₅ P ₃ O ₁₀ at boil for 2h	10.5			(F. Tianshun, 2017)

150g/L Naoh at 80°C for 45min	10.2			(F. Tianshun, 2017)
Treated with HNO ₃ + KCLO ₃	1320(320)	34.4(0.20)	2.33(0.54)	(P. Rawatan and S. F.S Buluh, 2018)
Treated with NaCLO	1160(190)	30.5(0.18)	2.29(0.22)	(P. Rawatan and S. F.S Buluh, 2018)
Treated with H ₂ O ₂ +Hac	1340(180)	30.2(0.22)	2.41(0.21)	(P. Rawatan and S. F.S Buluh, 2018)
Treated with NaOH	1450(360)	19.6(0.36)	2.49(0.17)	(P. Rawatan and S. F.S Buluh, 2018)
NaOH solution of higher conc.	329	22	2.35	(D.Chakrabo rty, 2006)
(6-25) % NaOH at RT for 2h	590-680	4.22-11.61	6.06-19.42	(Trujilo, 2014)
water retting	275	32	1.18	(S. Bhera and S. Kumar, 2018)(C. Manalo, 2015)
2-8wt NaOH FOR 1-24h	214-356.8	12.06-27.56	0.76-1.62	(S. Bhera and S. Kumar, 2018)
10wt%NaOH at 24h +RMT	368.33	55.24		(Shinde, 2018)
Treated with water at 100°C for 1h	209.4	10.77	1.64	(C. Ramprasad, 2018)
Treated with 5% NaOH solution at 65°C for 1h	234.7	12.22	1.93	(C. Ramprasad, 2018)
(1-3)wt% of NaOH	324-395	23.7-26.1	2.54-2.82	(Science, 2019)
(1-3)wt% of NaOH AT RT for 20min	780-811	40-48.5		(B. Lipp- symonowicz and S. Sztajnowski,

					2011)
Alkali+m ech	1.5N NaOH , heated for 5h at 70°C, pressed machine then steel nail was used	419	30	2.67	(D.Chakrabo rty, 2006)
		368.33	55.24		(Shinde, 2018)
Alkali+m ech	10wt%NaOH at 24h +RMT	644.8			(J. Fu, 2012)
CMT+alk ali	Width 1.5- 1.75, Thickness0.6 5-0.75, 0.1 N NaOH for 72h	370.1			(J. Fu, 2012)
RMT+alk ali	Length 8- 12cm, Thickness 0.75, 0.1N NaOH for 72h	370.1			(J. Fu, 2012)

➤ **Common method of extraction of polymer-**

- **Mechanical Extraction:**When mechanical extraction is used to separate polymers from natural sources, physical procedures like milling, pressing, or grinding are used. For instance, it is possible to mechanically break down plant cell walls and isolate the fibre cellulose structure in order to extract cellulose, a highly abundant polymer present in plants. Paper, textiles, and biological materials are just a few of the things that can be made with cellulose (T, 2012).
- **Chemical Extraction:**Chemical agents are used in chemical extraction to dissolve or modify natural sources in a certain way, making it easier to separate out the required polymers. It is usual practise to extract chitosan using techniques like alkaline treatment or enzymatic digestion. Chitosan is a natural polymer made from the chitin present in the exoskeletons of crustaceans . Chitosan has special qualities that make it useful in a variety of industries, including biomedicine, agriculture, and food packaging. These qualities include biocompatibility and biodegradability(Ravi Kumar, 2000).

- **Enzymatic Extraction:**Utilising specialised enzymes to dissolve intricate structures and liberate desirable polymers is known as enzymatic extraction. The removal of pullulan, a polysaccharide made by the fungus *Aureobasidium pullulans*, is one instance. The fungus's cell walls are disintegrated using enzyme hydrolysis, and further purifying procedures result in pure pullulan. Due to its film-forming and encapsulating qualities, pullulan is used in the food, pharmaceutical, and packaging sectors(Lim, 2018).
- **Acid Hydrolysis:**Acid hydrolysis is the process by which polymers are broken down by the action of acids. Acid hydrolysis can be used to remove pectin, a complex polymer presents in the cell walls of plants. Pectin can be released from plant material more easily when the links between its molecules are broken by acidic circumstances . Pectin is frequently utilised as a gelling agent, stabiliser, and dietary fibre in the food and pharmaceutical industries(D, 2008).
- **Alkaline Hydrolysis:**Alkaline solutions are used in alkaline hydrolysis to degrade polymers. Through alkaline hydrolysis, lignin, a complex polymer found in plant cell walls, can be removed. Lignin bonds are broken under alkaline circumstances, allowing it to be separated from other plant parts. Because it is renewable and aromatic, lignin has uses in the materials, chemicals, and biofuels industries(Sun, 2002).
- **Supercritical Fluid Extraction:**Utilising supercritical fluids, such as carbon dioxide, to extract polymers is known as supercritical fluid extraction. Using supercritical fluid extraction, for instance, natural rubber, a polymer made from the latex of the *Hevea Brasiliense*'s tree, can be extracted. This approach has benefits including minimum polymer degradation and solvent-free extraction . Numerous industries, including the automotive, medicinal, and industrial ones, use natural rubber(Mezzomo . N, 2010).

Extraction Method	Typers of plants for Extraction	Temp.(°c)	Polymers Extracted	Application	Ref.
Solvent Extraction	Aloe Vera	40-50	Carrageenan	Food Industry, Pharmaceuticals	(Sibusiso Alven, 2021)
Steam Distillation	Lavender	100-110	Linalool	Perfumery, Aromatherapy	(Marietta Biolon, 2019)
Soxhlet Extraction	Eucalyptus	60-80	Eucalyptol	Pharmaceuticals, Flavouring	(Angelo Luis, 2014)
Enzymatic Hydrolysis	Algae	35-45	Alginate	Biomedical, Food Additives	(Teketay Wassie, 2021)
Water Bath Extraction	Ginger	80-100	Gingerol	Nutraceuticals, Herbal Medicine	(Wenjing Hu, 2023)
Supercritical Fluid Extraction	Chamomile	50-70	Chamazulene	Cosmetics, Anti-inflammatory	(Yun-Lei Dai, 2023)
Microwave-Assisted Extraction	Green Tea Leaves	70-90	Catechins	Functional Foods, Antioxidants	(Khhomendra Kumar Sarwa, 2013)
Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction	Grape Seeds	40-60	Proanthocyanins'	Dietary Supplements, Skincare	(Juliano Garavaglia, 2016)
Cold Press Extraction	Sunflower Seeds	Room temp.	Sunflower oil	Culinary Uses, Cosmetics	(Shuangshuang Guo, 2017)
Fermentation	Corn or Sugarcane	varies	Polylactic Acid (PLA)	Bioplastics, Packaging, Textiles	(Chunhua Lou, 2021)(Annanya, 2021)

Some more sources of natural polymer:

Plant Sources			
S.no	Name of Plant	Polymer Name and Uses	Reference
1	Corn	used to produce biodegradable polymers like polylactic acid (PLA)	(Abdulrahman A.B.A Mohammed, 2022)
2	Sugarcane	used to produce biodegradable polymers such as cellulose-based materials	(Pol, 2017)
3	Flax	to create biodegradable polymers like linen and composite materials	(Md Shadin, 2019)
4	Hemp	used to produce biodegradable polymers(hemp bioplastic) and composite materials	(Khwanchat Promhuad, 2022)
5	Jute	to create biodegradable polymers and textiles	(Tribology of Natural Fiber Plymer Composites, 2008)
6	Bamboo	to produce biodegradable polymers(bamboo rayon) and composite materials	(Jing Su, 2018)
7	Sisal	to create biodegradable polymers and textiles	(Sisal reinforced polymer composites, 2008)
8	Kenaf	to produce biodegradable polymers and composite materials	(Mohd Saiful Asmal Rani, 2014)
9	Ramie	to create biodegradable polymers and textiles	(K.A. Dubey, 2017)
10	Cotton	to create textiles and various polymer-based products(cellulose	(Incorporated, n.d.)
11	Pine Trees	source of natural resins, such as rosin and turpentine, which have polymer-like properties and can be used in adhesives and coatings	(Mahendra, 2016)
12	Willow Trees	contains a natural polymer called salicylic acid, which is used in the production of aspirin and other pharmaceuticals	(Tia Lohtander, 2021)

13	Guar	Guar gum, extracted from the seeds of the guar plant, is a natural polymer used as a thickening and stabilizing agent in various industries	(Pankaj S. Waghere)
14	Acacia Trees	Acacia gum, also known as gum Arabic, is a natural polymer derived from the sap of acacia trees	(Seema, 2015)
15	Agarwood	Agarwood resin contains aromatic compounds that can be used in the production of perfumes and incense sticks	(Pooja Shivanad, 2022)
16	Agave	Agave fibres(sisal) can be processed to create biodegradable polymers and textiles	(Pooja Shivanad, 2022)
17	Kapok Tree	Kapok fibres from the seed pods can be used to produce natural insulation and padding materials	(Sangalang, 2021)
18	Sisal Hemp	Sisal fibres(sisal) can be processed to create biodegradable polymers and textiles	(Interaction, 2016)
19	Rubber Fig Tree	Latex from the rubber fig tree can be used to produce natural rubber	(Hunseung Kang, 2000)
Fruits and Vegetables			
1	Citrus Fruits	Pectin, a natural polymer, is found in the cell walls of citrus fruits such as oranges, lemons, and grapefruits. It is used as a gelling agent and stabilizer in food products	(Domenico Zannini, 2021)
2	Apple	Apples contain pectin, which can be extracted and used for various purposes including gelling and thickening agents	(Ines Calvete - Torre, 2021)
3	Carrots	Carrot pulp can be used to produce biodegradable polymer films	(Niloofar Hosseinvand, 2022)

4	Tomatoes	Tomato skins and peels contain lycopene, a natural pigment used in the production of biodegradable films and coatings	(Gauthies Mike L. Scavee, 2018)
5	Potatoes	Potato starch can be used to produce biodegradable polymers	(Hielko E. Grommers, 2016)
6	Cassava	Cassava starch can be used to produce biodegradable polymers like bioplastics	(Ahmed Edhirej, 2015)
7	Beets	Beet pulp can be used to produce biodegradable polymer films	(Pummerova, 2021)
8	Mangoes	Mango seeds contain a polymer called mango pectin, which can be used as a food thickener	(Malaiporn Wongkaew, 2021)
9	Guava	Guava seeds contain a viscous polymer that can be used for textile printing and as a thickening agent	(Borah, 2021)
10	Chia Seeds	Chia seeds contain mucilage, a natural polymer that can be used in food and pharmaceutical applications	(Masa Knez Hrcic, 2019)
11	Grapes	Grape skins and seeds contain a natural polymer called grape pomace, which can be used in the production of biodegradable films and coatings	(Lingxi Li, 2019)
12	Strawberries	Strawberry leaves and stems contain a polymer called ellagitannin, which has antioxidant properties and potential health benefits	(Ana Paula Bilck, 2010)
13	Pineapples	Pineapple leaves contain fibres that can be used to produce biodegradable textiles and composite materials	(Sinha, 2021)

14	Olives	Olive seeds contain a natural polymer called lignin, which can be used as a binder in the production of biodegradable materials	(Sara Valvez, 2021)
15	Kiwifruits	contains a natural polymer called pectin, which can be used in food products and as a thickening agent	(A.R. Ferguson, 2003)
16	Passion Fruit	Passion fruit seeds contain mucilage, a natural polymer that can be used in food and pharmaceutical applications	(Stephen T Talcott, 2003)
17	Jack fruit	Jackfruit seeds contain a natural polymer called jackfruit starch, which can be used in various applications such as food thickening and adhesive production	(Muhammad Najib Ahmad Marzuki, 2020)
18	Papaya	Papaya fruit latex contains a natural polymer called papain, which is used in the production of various enzymes and as a meat tenderizer	(Jaweria Ashfaq, 2022)
19	Cacao	a natural polymer called theobromine, which is used in the production of chocolate and other food products	(Allan Calmont de Andrade Almeida, 2021)
20	Aloe vera	Aloe vera gel contains polysaccharides, which are natural polymers with various applications in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	(Antoni Femenia, 1998)
Other Sources			
1	Soybeans	Soy protein can be processed to produce biodegradable polymers like soy-based plastics	(D.L.Kaplan)

2	Seaweed	to extract alginate, a natural polymer used in food, pharmaceuticals, and biomedical applications	(Jayachandran Venkatesan, 2016)
3	Animals(Connective Tissues)	Collagen is the polymer obtains from animals. Use in medical applications, cosmetics, food industry.	(A Eisenakh, 2021)
4	Silkworms	Silk obtained from silkworms is used in textiles, medical sutures	(Regina Ines Kunz, 2016)
5	Crustacean shells	Chitin is extracted from crustacean shell and used in biomedical applications, water purification	(Hamblin, 2016)
6	Bacteria	Bacterial Cellulose is used as biofilms, wound dressing	(Jonathan David Hinchliffe, 2021)
7	Milk	Casein, from milk is used as adhesives, edible films	(Wang, 2016)
8	Brown Algae	Alginate, from brown algae is used in food industry, pharmaceuticals, wound dressings	(Yanping Li, 2021)
9	Wool, Hair, Nails	Keratin is the polymer from wool, hair and nails. Used in textiles, cosmetics, biomedical applications	(Chaitanya Reddy Chilakamarry, 2021)
10	Wood	Lignin is the polymer obtain from wood. Used as binder, adhesives, fuel production.	(Manickam Ramesh, 2022)

Application in daily life :-

For civilized life we have some materials available like as steel, glass, wood, stone, brick, and concrete for most of the construction and wood, cotton, jute and some farming products for clothing or fabric preparation. Increasing the population, the rapid increase in demand of manufactured products introduce the new materials and that new materials are polymers or their derivatives and they impact on present way of life. e.g., polyethylene cups, fiberglass, clothes made from synthetic fibres, nylon bearings, plastic bags, polymer-based paints, epoxy glue, polyurethane foam cushion, silicon heart valves and

Teflon coated cookware and thinking about the ending of this list is impossible (Belgacem MN, 2011).

The natural and synthetic polymers are noticeably involved for human life for giving to comfort and facilitation and responsible for life itself, for medication, nutrition, communication, transportation, irrigation, container, clothing, recording history, buildings, highway etc. Imagination of human society without any type of polymer is difficult. It providing solution for critical problems of food, clean and abundant water, air, energy, and health (Belgacem MN, 2011)(Billmeyer, 1971).

Both synthetic and natural polymers could be used in the form of inorganic and organic polymers as coating, elastomer, adhesives blends, plastic, fibre, ceramic, caulks, and some composite. These polymers category is based on simple fundamental rules (N., 2009).

Application in parenteral :-

We have different types of polymers like methacrylic acid and methacrylic acid alkyl amide. Methacrylic acid is used as interferon inductor which work in cancer like disease and their alkyl amide derivative is work as plasma expander which rises the plasma level in human body. e.g., Insulin injection is used in diabetes and using different types of polymers in their preparation that act as reservoir which form bond with insulin and release their target site.

- **Weight loss effect :-** Chitosan used for replacing the calories in food and blood, that results is increasing the body weight (Darveshwar Jagdeep D).

Application in cosmetics :-

That are disclosed for the treatment of hair or skin, mainly a new quaternary chitosan derivative. These derivatives are used as a good substantively, particularly for hair keratin and for hair strengthening and hair conditioning. Some formulations are present in market e.g., oxidation hair colouring composition, hair toning composition, skin cream, hair setting lotion, hair treatment composition, gel form.

Application in conventional dosage forms -

- **Tablets** - In which polymer used for disintegrants and binder disintegrants such as starch, cellulose, alginates, polyvinyl pyrrolidone, sodium carboxy methyl cellulose which is used for reduction in the time of dissolution and it gives rapid action of drug. Binders such as ethyl cellulose, HPMC, Starch, Gelatine, Alginic acid, glucose, sucrose etc. which is used for bind the particles.
- **Capsules**- Different types of polymers are used as plasticizer on which the elasticity and strength of the gelatine are depend on it. It is used for controlling the release rate.
- **Film Coating Agent** - Chitosan's film used as a coating agent for traditional dosage form such as tablet the Siekkinen and cow workers studied the Chitosan used as gel forming excipient for metric types granules.
- **Natural Coating Agent** :-Shellac and Zein which is a natural polymer and used on large scale in present they requirement. Cellulose acetate phthalate and ethyl cellulose used in aqueous dispersion, non as pseudo latexes.
- **Disperse System** :- The emulsion, suspension which is biphasic liquid dosage form we, use different type of polymer for disperse one phase into another phase. Some polymer like polyvinyl pyrrolidone, ethyl cellulose.
- **Transdermal Drug Delivery System (Patches)** :- We use various types of polymers, the baking material also prepared using polymer for supporting the drug in drug reservoir. The process lignin extraction happens in the presence of an acid as proton donor in their chemical solubilization. This process complete in hot condition that promote hydrolysis reactions between the ligno-cellulosic sub-fraction.

The homogeneous diffusion of heat in the reactor happens in which water in the solvent extraction mixture facilitates. Ultimately, the lignin fractions which are extracted are solubilized in a solvent solution like as acetic acid or ethanol.

Material :- In Cameroon (Central Africa), from an industrial form the residues of banana rachis were collected before using, freshly banana rachis was sliced, dry through air until obtain constant Wight and coarsely grinded the chemical composition of banana rachis(Tiappi Deumaga, 2018).

Two methods use for lignin extraction from banana rachis. In first, method we use direct conduction heating involved formic acid/ acetic acid/water (FA solvent)and the second method using micro wave heating, it contains sulphuric acid/ethanol/water (SE

solvent) in SE extraction showed a greater extraction yield (58.7% Vs 45.3% for FAL) so, it has higher purity of the extracted lignin fraction (76.5%Vs71.0% FAL).In Summations extraction method allowed a greater pulp yield sometime ,it is taken as a better selectivity for lignin extraction thanks to the heating method of microwave. The SE lignin also shows greater thermostability their reason is its higher purity and greater density. Anit is stabilised the SE extraction method as effective for lignin extraction from banana rachis straw (sulphuric acid/ethanol/water solvent with micro wave heating). Despite, being depends on the application of the extracted lignin, for additional purification treatment requires the presence of sulphuric acid as residues(Tiappi Deumaga Mathias Floriana, 2019).

Banana Peel Extract Mediated Synthesis of gold nano particles:- The Gold nano particles are studied on large scale, it is easily synthesized and exhibit the surface plasmon resonance and shows higher chemical as thermal stability the structure including rods, hexagon, triangle, cubes, octagon, and nanowires synthesized using different types of techniques(T. Jennings, 2007)(N.R.Jana, 2001)(L. Wang, 2005)(D. Seo, 2006)(N. Pazos- Perez, 2008)

Recent Technology development:

- **Multi- Function, Self – Healing Hydrogel:**A hydrogel, a 3-D polymer that swells with water and has extra properties like electrical conductivity in addition to its "self-healing" qualities.

Researchers at the University of Manitoba have discovered a fresh technique for producing conductive polymer hydrogels that are mechanically stable. To generate a double-network hydrogel, chitosan (DCh-PPy) polymerizes acrylic acid utilising iron atoms; the iron also adds to the hydrogel's outstanding self-healing characteristics. The new material is very conductive, flexible, and highly pressure-sensitive, and it just needs a few minutes to "heal" entirely after being cut.

- **Stickier Super Glue:**A non-solvent glue that may be used to join elastic polymeric and watery materials together since it does not harden as it dries.

The possibility of a novel adhesive manufactured from cyanoacrylates that have been diluted with a non-solvent is being investigated by scientists at Johannes Kepler University Linz. The glue is "triggered" to polymerize by the water when it is exposed to a surface that contains water (like a hydrogel), which successfully entangles polymer chains with the connected substance(Chemicals, 2017).

- **The effect of polymer electrolyte on lithium-ion battery :-** In recent decades , in field of battery technologies which is grows and it is considerable progress , mainly as LIBs . It is use for the enhancement of the properties of electrodes and electrolytes; their resultant is use in development of the efficient electrochemical energy storage devices . LIB demand has been rising since 2017 from USD 29.86 billion and it is expected to the USD is reach 139.36 billion in 2026(Chen, et al., 2009)(Kang, Meng, Bréger, Grey, & Ceder, 2006). The LIB contains energy density and can commonly be enhanced through high - voltage active cathode materials , anode material and electrodes . It has a problem regarding high voltage cathodes and LIBs is decomposition of the electrolyte at more than 4.2 V Li/Li+(Manthiram, 2011)(Goriparti, et al., 2014)(Von Cresce & Xu, 2011)(Dedryvère, et al., 2010)(Brédas, Norton, Cornil, & Coropceanu, 2009).For develop the Li-ion conductivity, stability of the material further going and it has an impact of electrochemical parameter which is electrolyte that is used in implementation of next generation devices as higher cell potential . The rapidly development of power station and electric vehicles understand as safety and energy density engender and it is a major challenge for LIBs (. Dunn, Kamath, & Tarascon, 2011)(. Ding, Cano, Yu, Lu, & Chen, 2019)(Hao, Wang, & Xu, 2014). But we herein study the effect of different polymer electrolyte in different terms as physiochemical , thermal , electrical, and mechanical properties of LI -Battery(Liu, et al., 2020).

Conclusion: In conclusion, this comprehensive review illuminates the intricate world of polymers, traversing their synthesis, benefits of natural polymer in medicines, classifications, and practical applications across industries. From their indispensable role in paper, textiles, pharmaceutical and cosmetics to the promising horizons of advanced polymer procedures, the article exemplifies the polymers' versatility. Particularly, the spotlight on natural polymers underscores their pivotal significance in pharmaceuticals, offering heightened stability and diminished side effects. As we absorb the collective insights presented, let us recognize the untapped potential residing within polymer research. This amalgamation of knowledge beckons the scientific community to embrace these intricate structures as gateways to new frontiers of discovery. By fostering a deeper engagement with polymers, we hold the power to unravel mysteries, revolutionize industries, and inspire innovations yet to be imagined.

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